

BARRIERS IN BREASTFEEDING AMONG MOTHERS GIVING BIRTH UNDER DIFFERENT SETTINGS

Mahpara Sajid¹, Ayesha Habib², Zahid Bashir³, Nabeeha Zahid⁴, Sadia Khan⁵, Maria Haris⁶

¹Clinical nutritionist Affiliated with Abbott Nutrition international and Department of Nutritional sciences, Government college university Faisalabad

²Community Nutritionist, Affiliated with Abbott Nutrition International and Department of Nutritional Sciences, Government College University Faisalabad.

³PhD Scholar

³Department of Food and Nutritional Sciences, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴Student, Masters of Science in Information Security, Department of Information Security, National University of Science and Technology (NUST)

⁵Student University of Agriculture Faisalabad

⁶Associate Lecturer, Department of Food Science and Technology, University of Central Punjab, Lahore

¹mariaharis@ucp.edu.pk ²mahparasajid192@gmail.com, ³ayeshahabib036@gmail.com, ⁴zbsdk26@gmail.com, ⁵znabeeha08@gmail.com, ⁶sadia.khan.jhg@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Mahpara Sajid

Abstract

Globally, 2.7 million neonates die during 28 days of their lives. One of the reasons for the high mortality rate is improper breastfeeding practices. Late initiation of breastfeeding contributes to approximately 5.5 lac of neonatal deaths. Various studies indicated that adverse breastfeeding practices are mainly contributed to a number of factors i.e., C-section, late skin-to-skin contact, discard of colostrum, and pre-lacteal feeding. However, the relationship between these factors and inappropriate breastfeeding practices is least understood. Therefore, the aim of this study was to access the barriers in the initiation and exclusive breastfeeding among mothers giving birth under different settings in Faisalabad. In this study, about 300 postpartum mothers were included from different hospitals in Faisalabad. A well-researcher-administered questionnaire was used to collect data from mothers. Data was collected at two-point times i.e., firstly, after two days of delivery in a live interview regarding breastfeeding initiation, and secondly, after 4 months at phone calls about exclusive breastfeeding. Results showed that only 17.3% of mothers breastfeed their babies within 24 hours after birth, 71.3% of mothers continued breastfeeding after discharge from the hospital, and 23.3% of infants were exclusively breastfed for up to 6 months. The barriers found in lack of timely initiation of breastfeeding were C-section delivery (88.3%), lack of assistance from hospital staff (8.3%), lack of energy in mothers (69.3%), lack of milk production (23.3%). The barriers in exclusive breastfeeding were recommendation of formula milk by doctor (42.7%), lack of suggestions given by staff about how to resolve breastfeeding issues (97.3%). No significant association was found between socio-demographic factors and the practice of breastfeeding. Hence, Breastfeeding practices had a significant association with the C-section,

INTRODUCTION

The population of Pakistan is rapidly growing. There are an increasing number of modifiable risk factors for noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) among Pakistanis due to population growth, changes in food patterns, and a decline in physical activity. As a result of the rise in NCDs and the already common communicable diseases, Pakistan is dealing with twice as many ailments. This is evident from data on the global disease burden, which indicates that NCDs and injuries account for 62% of crude deaths and 77% of age-standardized deaths in Pakistan (Haris *et al.*, 2025). Neonatal time is the most vulnerable period of a human's life. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines the neonatal period as "starting at birth and terminating at 28 completed days of life. Neonatal mortality is the percentage of neonates who die before they reach the age of 28 days. It expresses the likelihood of an infant born in a certain year or period dying before the age of 28 days if subjected to the era's age-specific mortality rates. This is expressed as a percentage of live births (Roser *et al.*, 2013). Worldwide, about 2.7 million neonates die during the first 28 days of their lives. Moreover, every 3rd of these newborn deaths happens on the 1st day, and three-quarters occur in the first six days of their lives (Raihana *et al.*, 2019). Only ten nations, predominantly in Asia, account for two-thirds of all newborn deaths worldwide. Pakistan ranked third among these countries. Pakistan is estimated for 7% of worldwide neonatal death, with an average of 298000 deaths per year and an estimated neonatal mortality rate of 49 per 1000 live births (Jehan *et al.*, 2009). According to 2013, the first week of life is very critical for a neonate, as 36% of deaths (one million) happen during the first 24 hours after delivery, 37% (one million) in the early neonatal period, and 27% (0.8 million) happen between 7 and 27 days of life (Lehtonen *et al.*, 2017). In 2018, about 4.0 million children died in their first year of birth, accounting for 75% of all fatalities among children under the age of five (Sankar *et al.*, 2015).

To lessen the burden of neonates and infant mortality, WHO has proposed a package of

interventions, including breastfeeding. Breastfeeding is a very important and useful feeding technique in infancy that is linked to lowering the rate of mortality in neonates and decreasing morbidity such as pneumonia, diarrhea, and neonatal sepsis, as well as diabetes and obesity in later life (Takahashi *et al.*, 2017 ; Gridneva *et al.*, 2019). Undoubtedly early initiation of breastfeeding has nutritional, developmental, psychological, and immunological, benefits for infants and mothers (Grace *et al.*, 2017; Berde and Yalcin, 2016; Adreas *et al.*, 2015). Breastfeeding should be started as soon as possible after birth preferably within one hour, as recommended by WHO (Sharma and Byrne, 2016; Huang *et al.*, 2019). Recent research-based studies examined that ideal breastfeeding practices could prevent about 12% of child deaths under 5 years, estimating around eighty lac lives in low- and middle-income countries (Sankar *et al.*, 2015).

Delayed breastfeeding initiation has been associated with an increase in the risk of newborn morbidity and mortality. A lot of factors that delay breastfeeding initiation include late skin-to-skin connection, C-section, lack of breast milk production, mother illness, lack of support from hospital staff, and lack of awareness (Mukunya *et al.*, 2017). Skin-to-skin contact between newborn and mother has a lot of protective benefits, but unfortunately, it is an unappreciated intervention (Singh *et al.*, 2017).

Infants should be exclusively breastfed for the first six months of their lives and continued up to two years along with complementary feeding, as recommended by WHO. Exclusive breastfeeding is very important to ensure good health, growth, and development of children to reach their full potential in later life (Lawrence and Lawrence, 2021). About 6 months of exclusive breastfeeding has several advantages, including a lower risk of pneumonia, gastrointestinal infection, otitis media, and urinary tract infection in the infant, as well as faster return to pre-pregnancy weight and lower risk of developing type 2 diabetes in the mother (Motee and Jeewon, 2014).

Globally, only half of all mothers practice early initiation of breastfeeding (Mukunya *et al.*, 2017). In 128 countries, early initiation of breastfeeding prevalence ranges from 14% to 95% with approximately an average of 64%, and half of these countries have less than 50% prevalence (Takahashi *et al.*, 2017). The survey data from developing countries showed that the exercise of exclusive breastfeeding to infants younger than 6 months had risen in 2010 as compared to 1995, from 33% to 39% respectively (Cai *et al.*, 2012). The rate of early initiation of breastfeeding increased from 37.7% to 48% from 2011 to 2018, bringing Pakistan closer to the 50% target set by the World Health Assembly (NNS, 2018).

Methodology

Study setting and targeted population

The longitudinal survey-based study was conducted in the gynecology ward of different hospitals in Faisalabad from August to February 2022. A total of 8 main private and government hospitals were selected to collect data which majorly included maternity hospitals. Three-Hundred postpartum mothers were included in this study who met the specific selection criteria i.e., Mothers who delivered their babies 1 or 2 days before the interview, and mothers who had access to the phone (required for the further data collection on phone calls).

Permission letters were written with all details, importance, and general ethics of research and presented to the Medical Superintendent (MS) of hospitals and Head of Department (HOD) of gynecology wards to get access to their domains. Basic details were briefly explained to participants before the interview i.e., need, benefits, risks, the confidentiality of the given information, and the voluntary nature of participation in the study. Unwilling women were not forced to participate in the study.

Data collection

A well researcher-administered questionnaire was used to collect data about breastfeeding practices in the hospital and on phone calls after 4 months of discharge in the study population group. The data was collected at 2-point times. The initial data was

collected face to face after 1 to 2 days of delivery. Questions were asked regarding experiences during pregnancy and problems faced during the initiation of breastfeeding. The final data was collected on phone calls. Questions were asked regarding barriers faced in exclusive breastfeeding and the type of milk on which the baby is relying. The questionnaire included both open-ended and close-ended questions. The interview lasted for about 20 minutes during the first data collection and 5 to 7 minutes during the final data collection on phone calls. The questionnaire had four main components i.e., socioeconomic status, experiences during pregnancy, barriers in early initiation of breastfeeding, and barriers in exclusive breastfeeding.

Statistical analysis

The data regarding experiences during pregnancy and barriers in breastfeeding were analyzed by using SPSS software version 26. Initially, descriptive statistics was applied to estimate the frequencies of different variables. In bivariate analysis, a Chi-square test was used to check the association of socio-demographic factors (Khasawneh *et al.*, 2020), experiences during pregnancy, and experiences in the hospital after delivery with initial and exclusive breastfeeding. Multivariate logistic regression was applied to quantify the association between the variables of interest (derived from bivariate analysis) and initial and exclusive breastfeeding (Montgomery, 2017).

Results and discussions

Characteristics of participants

Socio-demographic and pregnancy related characteristics of mothers

Looking into the socio-demographic characteristics of the study population, 59.7% of mother were educated, 4.7% were employed, 65.3% of participants lived in urban areas, 79.7% lived in joint family system, 19.3% had moderate socio-economic status. Viewing the experiences of women during pregnancy, 30.3% had deliver their first baby, 15% had fertility treatment with the current pregnancy, 50% had medical issues during pregnancy, 46.3% had 9 to 15 antenatal visits and

32.7% received guidance by health professionals regarding breastfeeding during antenatal visits.

Characteristics of mothers during delivery in hospital

In the study population, 4.3% of mothers gave breast milk as a first feed of the baby, 17.3% of mothers breastfeed their babies within 24 hours after birth and only 2.7% had exclusive breastfeeding for 2 days. A total of 88.3% of mothers had C-section delivery, 43.3% faced complications during delivery, 44.3% had gestational age of 37 weeks, 21.3% held their baby within 24 hours, 81% held the baby for less than 30 minutes, 69.3% didn't held the baby due to lack of energy, 8.3% of mothers received help and guidance from hospital staff regarding breastfeeding. A majority of mother (99%) planned to breastfeed their babies' priors to birth, and 51% of mothers had 24-hour rooming-in with their babies. Pre-lacteal feed was very common as 42.3% of mothers practiced pre-lacteal feed, 45.3% discarded colostrum.

The rate of exclusive breastfeeding was 23.3% among mothers, and 71.3% continued breastfeeding after discharge along with other milk resources. About 42.7% of mothers were advised to use infant formula by doctors. In the study population, 26% of babies had diarrheal episodes due to infant formula consumption.

Barriers in the initiation of breastfeeding

A total of 211 mothers didn't feed their babies due to c-section delivery, 259 mothers didn't receive any assistance from the hospital staff, 82 mothers lack enough production of milk, and 58 mothers were far away for their babies. Moreover, 199 of mother had c-sections lack of assistance from hospital staff, 70 mothers had less milk production and lack of assistance from hospital staff, 18 mothers had c-section and their babies are also far away from them, and 49 mothers didn't get any assistance from hospital staff and their babies were far away from them. The conclusion got from this research that C-section (n=211) and lack of assistance from hospital staff (n=259) were main barriers in early initiation of breastfeeding.

Table 4.1. Frequency of mothers based on the barriers in the initiation of breastfeeding

	C-section	Lack of help from hospital staff	No/less milk production	The baby was not with the mother	Total
C-section	211	199	49	18	211
Lack of help from hospital staff	199	259	70	49	259
No/less milk production	49	70	82	0	82
The baby was not with the mother	18	49	0	58	58
Total	211	259	82	58	288

Mixed milk feeding under six months (MixMF)

After got discharge from hospital, 23.3% of mothers exclusively breastfed their babies and a total of 76.7% of mothers used other than breast

milk source like formula milk, cow milk, and complementary feeding (4.3%). The results of mixed milk feeding are shown in the figure no 1.1.

Figure no 1.1. Mixed milk feeding under six months

A systemic review highlighted the highest prevalence of MixMF in Asia with sustained high rates across 6 months of age. The identified major drivers for preferring MixMF over EBF were insecurity of mothers about satisfying infant's needs breastfeeding in public, to avoid exclusive formula feeding, to have social flexibility, perceived advantages, cultural belief, maternal health issues etc. (Mongo-Montero *et al.*, 2020). The results were justified by a study held in Malawi, where the percentage of mixed breastfeeding and predominant breastfeeding were 36% and 21% respectively (Kuchenbecker *et al.*, 2015).

The results were compared with a study demonstrated that mothers with secondary education and antenatal visits in health facilities had initiated breastfeeding within an hour after birth. On the other hand, the mothers who had less education didn't find to practice early initiation of breastfeeding. However, the mother's age and parity didn't have any association with the early initiation of breastfeeding. So, it was concluded that mother's education didn't find any association with breastfeeding initiation in the recent research, but the association was clear in the previous study (Ogunlesi, 2010).

Maternal factors and First feed of the baby
Association between sociodemographic factors and 1st feed of the baby

Bivariate association between sociodemographic information and the first feed of the baby has been shown in Table 4.2. The Chi-square test signifies that the sociodemographic factors were not significantly associated with the first feed of the baby. The sociodemographic factor included the mother's age, level of education, employment status, father's occupation, socioeconomic status, type of family, and place of residence. The results obtained from this research showed that there was no association ($p > 0.05$) of a single sociodemographic factor with baby's first feed.

Association between experiences during pregnancy and first feed of the baby

Bivariate association between maternal experiences during pregnancy and the first feed of the baby has been shown in Table 4.3. The results declared that there was no association of number of pregnancies ($p=0.458$), number of miscarriages ($p=0.47$), fertility treatment ($p=0.45$), and the number of antenatal visits ($p=0.314$) with the early initiation of breastfeeding. Besides the association was found in medical problems during pregnancy ($p=0.047$) and information given regarding breastfeeding initiation during antenatal visits ($p=0.023$) with early breastfeeding initiation. The obtained results were similar to the results of a study performed to check the association between maternal obesity and

early breastfeeding initiation (Amir and Donath 2007).

Multinomial regression was applied for adjusting the potential confounders in the model. Medical problem during pregnancy was not statistically significant ($p= 0.198$). However, in the statistical analysis, information during antenatal visits was highly associated with the first feed of the baby ($p< 0.001$). Table 4.5. shows multivariate association between maternal factor and the first feed of the baby.

Association between the experiences in the hospital during delivery and the first feed of the baby

The association between experiences in hospital during delivery and the first feed of the baby has been described in the Table 4.4. In the statistical analysis, type of delivery, how long after birth did the mother hold baby, the reason for not holding the baby after birth, help by staff during first feeding, and 24-hour rooming-in had a highly significant association ($p< 0.001$) with the early initiation of breastfeeding. Complications during delivery and no practice of pre-lacteal feeding was associated with the breastfeeding initiation in early stage. However, gestational age ($p=0.602$), and discard of colostrum ($p=0.099$) didn't have any association with early initiation of breastfeeding.

Multinomial regression was applied for adjusting the potential confounders in the model. In the statistical analysis, the help by staff in first breastfeeding, 24-hour rooming-in, and pre-lacteal feeding had positive association with early initiation of breastfeeding. Table 4.5. shows

multivariate association between maternal factor regarding experiences during hospital after delivery and early initiation of the breastfeeding.

The obtained results were compared with various previous research to check the accuracy of work. In a study, the mothers who had C-section have more breastfeeding difficulties (40%) as compared with vaginal delivery (29%) (Hobbs *et al.*, 2016). In another study the mothers who received proper help from hospital staff and phone number to call for the discussion of any problem regarding breastfeeding had a very low percentage of breastfeeding termination before the completion of 2 months of age (Schliep *et al.*, 2019). The results obtained from a cross sectional survey declared that the practice of prelacteal feeding reduce the chances of early initiation of breastfeeding (Dubik and Amegah, 2021). The result of these studies was similar to the results obtained from the recent study. Hence, it was concluded that these factors had truly impact on the early initiation of breastfeeding. Another study conducted in Uganda, supported the results of recent study. A total of 31.3% of mothers delayed the initiation of breastfeeding. The factors associated with delayed breastfeeding were inadequate antenatal guidance (OR 3.6; 95% CI 1.9-6.8), HIV positive status of mother (OR 2.3; 95% CI 1.3-4.2), C-section delivery (OR 8.6; 95% CI 4.7-16) lack of professional assistance to start breastfeeding (OR 1.8; 95% CI 1.2-2.8). The other reasons include less milk production, negative cultural beliefs, and lack of energy in mother to feed baby after delivery (Kalisa *et al.*, 2015).

Table 4.2. Association between socioeconomic factors and 1st feed of the baby

		1 st feed of the baby			Test statistics	
		Mother milk	Infant formula	Total	Chi-square value	p-value
Mother's age (years)	15 to 25	2	117	119	$\chi^2 = 3.506$	0.173 ^{NS}
	26 to 35	10	59	169		
	>35	1	11	12		
Level of education	Illiterate	0	31	31	$\chi^2 = 2.749$	0.25 ^{NS}
	≤ Metric	5	136	141		
	≤ Graduate	8	120	128		
Employment status	Employed	0	14	14	$\chi^2 = 0.665$	0.46 ^{NS}
	Non-employed	13	273	286		
Father's occupation	Government job	2	20	22	$\chi^2 = 3.556$	0.314 ^{NS}
	Private job	5	76	81		
	Business	4	83	87		
	Labour	2	108	110		
Socioeconomic status	Low	9	218	227	$\chi^2 = 0.370$	0.831 ^{NS}
	Middle	3	55	58		
	High	1	14	15		
Type of family	Nuclear	5	56	61	$\chi^2 = 2.79$	0.097 ^{NS}
	Joint	8	231	239		
Place of residence	Urban	9	187	196	$\chi^2 = 0.081$	0.775 ^{NS}
	Rural	4	99	103		

Association between experiences during pregnancy and the 1st feed of the baby

		1 st feed of the baby			Test statistics	
		Mother milk	Infant formula	Total	Chi-square value	p-value
		No of pregnancies	1	4	87	91
	2	1	64	65		
	3	4	50	54		
	4	3	41	44		
	≥5	1	45	46		
No of miscarriages	0	11	218	229	$\chi^2 = 1.51$	0.47 ^{NS}
	1	2	39	41		
	≥2	0	30	30		
Fertility treatment	Yes	1	44	45	$\chi^2 = 0.569$	0.45 ^{NS}
	No	12	243	255		
Medical problems during pregnancy	Yes	3	147	150	$\chi^2 = 3.940$	0.047*
	No	10	140	150		
No. of antenatal visits	1 to 8	11	137	148	$\chi^2 = 3.556$	0.314 ^{NS}
	9 to 15	1	138	139		
	>15	1	12	13		
Information given regarding breastfeeding initiation during antenatal visits	Yes	8	90	98	$\chi^2 = 5.150$	0.023*
	No	5	197	202		

^{NS}Non significant

*Significant

^{NS}Non significant

Table 4.4. Association between the experiences in the hospital during delivery and the 1st feed of the baby

		1 st feed of the baby			Test statistics	
		Mother milk	Infant formula	Total	Chi-square value	p-value
Type of delivery	Normal	7	28	35	23.45	<0.001**
	C-section	6	259	265		
Complications during delivery	Yes	2	128	130	$\chi^2 = 4.32$	0.038*
	No	11	159	170		
Gestational age	< 37 weeks	2	77	79	$\chi^2 = 1.015$	0.602 _{NS}
	= 37 weeks	6	127	133		
	>37 weeks	5	83	88		
How long after birth did the mother hold baby	Within 24 hours	10	54	64	$\chi^2 = 25.13$	<0.001**
	Within 1 to 2 days	2	114	116		
	After 3 days	1	119	120		
The reason for not holding the baby after birth	Baby required observation	3	75	78	$\chi^2 = 57.62$	<0.001**
	Mother didn't have energy	4	204	208		
	Held immediately	6	7	13		
Staff assistance during breastfeeding	Yes	4	21	25	$\chi^2 = 8.95$	0.003*
	No	9	266	275		
24-hour rooming-in	Yes	11	142	153	$\chi^2 = 6.14$	0.013*
	No	2	145	147		
Prelacteal feed	Yes	2	125	127	$\chi^2 = 4.04$	0.044*
	No	11	162	173		
Discard of colostrum	Yes	3	133	136	$\chi^2 = 2.716$	0.099 _{NS}
	No	10	154	164		

^{NS}Non significant

*Significant

^{NS}Non significant

Table 4.5. Multivariate association between maternal factors and the first feed of the baby

1 st feed of the baby		B	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp (B)	95% Confidence Interval	
								Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Mother feed	Intercept	-5.253	2.428	4.680	1	0.031			
	Type of delivery (Normal)	-0.107	1.445	0.005	1	0.941 ^{NS}	0.899	0.053	15.262
	Type of delivery (C-section)	0 ^b			0				
	Complications during delivery (Yes)	0.162	1.019	0.025	1	0.874 ^{NS}	1.176	0.160	8.662
	Complications during delivery (No)	0 ^b			0				
	Medical problem during pregnancy (Yes)	-1.409	1.654	1.654	1	0.198 ^{NS}	0.244	0.029	2.092
	Medical problem during pregnancy (No)	0 ^b			0	0.130 ^{NS}	4.065	0.663	24.939
	Information given in antenatal visits (Yes)	1.403	2.297	2.297	1	0.007**	105.811	3.541	3161.518
	Information given in antenatal visits (No)	0 ^b			0	0.313 ^{NS}	4.821	0.227	102.584
	How long after birth did the mother hold the baby (Within 24 hours)	4.662	1.733	7.233	1	0.761 ^{NS}	0.592	0.020	17.371
	How long after birth did the mother hold the baby (Within 1 to 2 days)	1.573	1.560	1.017	1	0.046*	0.018	0.000	0.932
	How long after birth did the mother hold the baby (After 3 days)	0 ^b			0	0.025*	16.866	1.436	198.106
	The reason for not holding the baby after birth	-0.525	1.724	0.093	1	0.761 ^{NS}	0.592	0.020	17.371

The reference category is infant formula. This parameter is set to zero because it is a reductant. Maternal factors and exclusive breastfeeding
4.6.1. Association between sociodemographic factors and exclusive breastfeeding

The association between sociodemographic information and exclusive breastfeeding has been shown in Table 4.6. The Chi-square test signifies that level of education, employment status, type of family and the place of residence were not significantly associated with exclusive breastfeeding. However, the affordability of formula milk and father’s occupation were highly associated ($p < 0.001$) with exclusive breastfeeding. It was concluded by the result that the parents who can afford formula milk, they did not prefer mother milk as the consumption of formula milk is far easy for baby as compared to mother milk. Beside the parents who could not afford formula milk, they didn’t have any other better options except mother milk.

Multinomial regression was applied for adjusting the potential confounders in the model. Father’s occupation had no association with exclusive breastfeeding as the data was subjected to multinomial

regression model. However, in the statistical analysis, affordability of formula milk was highly associated with exclusive breastfeeding ($p < 0.001$). Table 4.9. shows multivariate association between maternal factor and exclusive breastfeeding.

Numerous researches conducted in Kenya have identified a variety of variables as potential determinants of exclusive breastfeeding. The data was obtained from 20 papers. The factors that were associated with exclusive breastfeeding; sociodemographic, socioeconomic, socio-cultural, maternal, psychosocial, and social support factors. It is important to scale up strategies for increasing exclusive breastfeeding that target sociodemographic, socioeconomic, socio-cultural, maternal, psychosocial, and social support factors. Additionally, it is strongly advised to use behavior change communication to promote healthy exclusive breastfeeding practices (Mututho *et al.*, 2017).

4.6.2. Association between experiences during pregnancy and exclusive breastfeeding

The association between maternal experiences during pregnancy and exclusive breastfeeding has been shown in the Table 4.7. The results obtained from this research showed that there was no association ($p > 0.05$) of a single factor with exclusive breastfeeding. A study performed to examine the impact of stress during pregnancy on the duration of breastfeeding. Independent of maternal sociodemographic factors and biological determinants, stressful life events during pregnancy increased the chances of early termination of breastfeeding. Financial difficulties, stress related to separation or divorce, and moving during pregnancy were significant predictors of a shorter breastfeeding duration (Li *et al.*, 2008). The results of this study didn't match to the recent study.

4.6.3. Association between the experiences in the hospital during delivery and exclusive breastfeeding

The association between experiences in hospital during delivery and exclusive breastfeeding has been described in the Table 4.8. In the statistical analysis, the factors like type of delivery, gestational age, plan of feeding prior to birth, the first feed of the baby, exclusive breastfeeding for first two days and discard of colostrum didn't have any association with exclusive

breastfeeding. Besides, pre-lacteal feeding ($p=0.042$), recommendation of formula milk by doctor ($p=0.014$), staff advice regarding positioning before discharge ($p<0.001$), suggestions given by staff about how to overcome breastfeeding difficulties ($p<0.001$) had association with exclusive breastfeeding.

Multinomial regression was applied for adjusting the potential confounders in the model. In the statistical analysis, recommendation of formula milk by doctor and staff assistance regarding breastfeeding positioning had positive association with exclusive breastfeeding. Table 4.9. shows multivariate association between maternal factor regarding experiences during hospital after delivery and exclusive breastfeeding. In a cross-sectional study, it was examined that the strongest factors that promote breastfeeding were the education and counseling skills of the staff of maternity ward, vaginal delivery, 24-hour rooming-in, and the success of initial breastfeeding. Furthermore, need of counseling regarding breastfeeding, and use of nipple shield also effect exclusive breastfeeding. It was revealed that medical issue of mother or infant caused delay in breastfeeding (Hakala *et al.*, 2021).

Table 4.6. Association between socioeconomic factors and exclusive breastfeeding

		Exclusive breastfeeding			Test statistics	
		Yes	No	Total	Chi-square value	p-value
Mother's age (years)	15 to 25	30	89	119	$\chi^2 = 0.449$	0.779 ^{NS}
	26 to 35	37	132	169		
	>35	3	9	12		
Level of education	Illiterate	10	24	34	$\chi^2 = 4.106$	0.128 ^{NS}
	≤ Metric	37	104	121		
	≤ Graduate	23	105	118		
Employment status	Employed	3	11	14	$\chi^2 = 0.030$	0.863 ^{NS}
	Non-employed	67	219	286		
Affordability of formula milk	Yes	19	128	147	$\chi^2 = 17.45$	< 0.001**
	No	51	102	123		
Father's occupation job	Government job	5	17	22	$\chi^2 = 12.81$	0.005**
	Private	14	67	81		
	Business	13	74	87		
	Labour	38	72	110		
Type of family	Nuclear	12	49	61	$\chi^2 = 0.574$	0.449 ^{NS}
	Joint	58	181	239		
Place of residence	Urban	42	154	196	$\chi^2 = 0.871$	0.351 ^{NS}
	Rural	27	76	103		

Table 4.7. Association between experiences during pregnancy and exclusive breastfeeding

		Exclusive breastfeeding			Test statistics	
		Yes	No	Total	Chi-square value	p-value
No of pregnancies	1	22	69	91	$\chi^2 = 5.84$	0.211 ^{NS}
	2	12	53	65		
	3	27	37	54		
	4	6	38	44		
	≥5	13	33	46		
No of miscarriages	0	55	174	229	$\chi^2 = 2.01$	0.365 ^{NS}
	1	11	30	41		
	≥2	4	26	30		
Fertility treatment	Yes	9	36	45	$\chi^2 = 0.329$	0.566 ^{NS}
	No	61	194	255		
Medical problems during pregnancy	Yes	37	113	150	$\chi^2 = 0.298$	0.585 ^{NS}
	No	33	117	150		

^SNon significant

^{NS}Non significant

Table 4.8. Association between the experiences in the hospital during delivery and exclusive breastfeeding

		Exclusive breastfeeding			Test statistic	
		Yes	No	Total	Chi-square value	p-value
Type of delivery	Normal	5	30	35	$\chi^2 = 1.81$	0.178 ^{NS}
	C-section	65	200	265		
Gestational age	< 37 weeks	16	63	79	$\chi^2 = 1.86$	0.395 ^{NS}
	= 37 weeks	29	104	133		
	>37 weeks	25	63	88		
Plan of feeding prior to birth	Yes	69	228	297	$\chi^2 = 0.169$	0.681 ^{NS}
	No	1	2	3		
The first feed of the baby	Mother milk	2	11	13	$\chi^2 = 0.480$	0.488 ^{NS}
	Infant formula	68	219	287		
Exclusive breastfeeding for 1 st 2 days	Yes	2	6	88	$\chi^2 = 0.013$	0.910 ^{NS}
	No	68	224	292		
Prelacteal feed	Yes	37	90	127	$\chi^2 = 4.14$	0.042*
	No	33	140	173		
Discard of colostrum	Yes	35	101	136	$\chi^2 = 0.802$	0.370 ^{NS}
	No	35	129	164		
Did the doctor recommend formula milk	Yes	21	107	128	$\chi^2 = 5.98$	0.014*
	No	49	123	172		
Staff advice regarding positioning before discharge	Yes	11	7	18	$\chi^2 = 15.27$	<0.001**
	No	59	223	282		
Is the staff given any suggestions about how to resolve breastfeeding issues	Yes	5	3	8	$\chi^2 = 7.04$	<0.001**
	No	65	227	292		

Table 4.9. Multivariate association between maternal factors and exclusive breastfeeding

Exclusive breastfeeding		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp (B)	95% Confidence Interval	
								Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Yes	Intercept	-0.494	0.229	2.725	1	0.099			
	Affordability of formula milk (Yes)	-0.992 0 ^b	0.320	9.627	1 0	0.002**	0.371	0.198	0.694
	Affordability of formula milk (No)	-0.187 -0.661	0.581 0.385	0.103 2.954	1 1	0.748 ^{NS} 0.086 ^{NS}	0.830 0.516	0.265 0.243	2.593 1.097
	Father's occupation (Government Job)	-0.767 0 ^b	0.384	3.978	1 0	0.046*	0.465	0.219	0.987
	Father's occupation (Private job)	0.397 0 ^b	0.301	1.739	1 0	0.187 ^{NS}	1.487	0.824	2.683
	Father's occupation (Business)	-0.638	0.315	4.108	1	0.043*	0.528	0.285	0.979
	Father's occupation (Labour)				0				
	Prelacteal feed (Yes)	0 ^b	0.589	7.562	1	0.006**	5.056	1.593	16.051
	Prelacteal feed (No)				0	0.582 ^{NS}	1.696	0.258	11.127
	Did the doctor recommend formula milk (Yes)	1.621 0 ^b	0.960	0.303	1 0				
	Did the doctor recommend formula milk (No)	0.528 0 ^b							
	Staff assist regarding positioning (Yes)								
	Staff assist regarding positioning (No)								
	Any suggestion by staff to resolve problems faced during breastfeeding (Yes)								
	Any suggestion by staff to resolve problems faced during breastfeeding (No)								

*Significant

**Highly significant

^{NS}Non significant

The reference category is No

This parameter is set to zero because it is a reductant

Discussions

In the selected mothers who delivered their babies in the maternity wards of different hospitals in Faisalabad, it was evaluated that, the information given regarding breastfeeding initiation during antenatal visits, holding time of baby after birth, assistance of medical staff during breastfeeding in hospital, 24-hours of rooming-in were positively associated with the early initiation with breastfeeding. On the other hand, C-section, complications during delivery, medical problems during pregnancy, and pre-lacteal feeding practices were inversely associated with early breastfeeding initiation. Furthermore, there was no association found between age, employment status, level of education, type of family, place of residence, father's occupation, socio-economic status, no of pregnancies, no of antenatal visits, gestational age and discard of colostrum with early initiation of breastfeeding. After the collection of data on phone calls regarding continuation of breastfeeding or exclusive breastfeeding, it was concluded that the staff's advice regarding positioning before discharge and suggestions given by staff about how to resolve breastfeeding issues were positively associated with exclusive breastfeeding. Affordability of formula milk, father's occupation, recommendation of formula milk by doctor and prelacteal feeding practices were inversely associated with exclusive breastfeeding. In addition, there was no association found between sociodemographic factors, pregnancy related factors like medical problem during pregnancy, no of pregnancies, no of miscarriages, no of antenatal visits, and experience during delivery in hospital like type of delivery, 1st feed of the baby, exclusive breastfeeding for 1st 2 days, gestational age, plan of feed prior to birth and discard of colostrum with the exclusive breastfeeding.

The results of present study demonstrated that the rate of breastfeeding initiation was low as compared with a previous study conducted in Lira district, located in Northern Uganda (Mukunya *et al.*, 2017). The percentage of mothers who started breastfeeding within 24 hours was 17.3%, comparable to previous study which had almost 3 times high rate of breastfeeding initiation (44.8%). According to a secondary analysis conducted using the WHO Global Survey on mother and infant health, the

prevalence of early breastfeeding initiation varied greatly amongst countries, ranging from 17.6% to 98.5% with the average of 57.6% (Takahashi *et al.*, 2017). The data obtained from 2015 to 2016 India national family health survey demonstrated that 41.5% of mothers started breastfeeding within an hour after birth (Senanyake *et al.*, 2019). According to the data taken from Bangladesh Demographic and Health Survey (BDHS) held in 2014, the prevalence rate of breastfeeding initiation among mothers in Bangladesh was 51.4% (Islam *et al.*, 2019). A study in middle east demonstrated that only 34.3% of mothers-initiated breastfeeding within an hour of birth while the exclusive breastfeeding rate was reduced to 20% only (Alzaheb and R.A., 2017).

The research findings of the current studies were significantly high exclusive breastfeeding rate, compared to the previous studies. According to the longitudinal survey conducted in Austria, at one week of age 55% of babies were exclusively breastfed, which dropped to 1.9% after 6 months. The percentage was very low as compared with the exclusive breastfeeding rate in recent study (23.3%) up to 6 months (Burger *et al.*, 2012). The results of a national representative survey in China showed 20.7% rate of exclusive breastfeeding under 6 months of age (Duan *et al.*, 2018). According to the 2 rounds of National Health Family Survey (NHFS), the percentage of breastfeeding under 6 months was 46.3% and 48.6% in NFHS-1 and NFHS-3 respectively. The percentage of breastfeeding declined along with the addition of months, i.e., at 4th month, only 24% and 31% of infants were exclusively breastfed in NFHS-1 and NFHS-3 respectively (Burger *et al.*, 2012).

Exclusively breastfed infants have more subcortical grey matter and white matter volume than formula-fed infants, according to brain neuroimaging studies. Breast milk contains the carotenoids and natural form of tocopherol that are deposited in brain. Lutein is the most abundant carotenoid in breast milk, but it is absent from most infant formulas, while the synthetic form of tocopherol is present in formula milks (Liu *et al.*, 2019). A study was conducted to check the effect of breastfeeding on neurological development in very preterm infants showed positive results. The results showed that the infants who were exclusively breastfed for first 28

days of life had higher volume of deep nuclear grey matter at term equivalent. Furthermore, at the age of 7 years, better working memory, IQ, academic achievements, and motor functions were examined in them (Belfort *et al.*, 2016). According to another study it was seen that, at six months, better communication, and social interaction, while at 12 months, better communication, social interaction and cognition were observed in the four months exclusively breastfed baby as compared with formula feeding or non-breastfed infant (Choi *et al.*, 2018).

A study was performed to identify the relationship between mode of feeding with body composition and anthropometric measurements of infant at the age of six months. Results showed that the body fat percent and trunk fat mass were high, and fat free mass was less in breastfed infant as compared with formula fed infants at the age of 6 months. These findings support recent research studies that found formula-fed newborns have more fat-free mass throughout the first six months of life (Tahir *et al.*, 2021).

A study elaborated the importance of breastfeeding over formula feeding in preterm babies with different gestational ages. Results indicated that breastfeeding preterm infants with a gestational age of 28 to 30 weeks had a considerably faster growth in body weight, a much-reduced incidence rate of NEC, a substantially higher ALP level, and a significantly lower Alb level than the formula feeding group. On the other hand, the breastfeeding group had a much faster gain in body weight, a considerably reduced incidence rate of feeding intolerance, a significantly shorter hospital stays, and a much higher ALP level in preterm infants with a gestational age of 31 to 33 weeks (Li *et al.*, 2017). Another longitudinal study was conducted to assess the association between breastfeeding duration and infant development in south Korea. This study included 255 infants along with their mothers. The data regarding breastfeeding was collected at four and six months, while the milestones of infant development were measured at the age of 6 and 12 months.

In the present study, C-section was the main barrier in the initiation of breastfeeding. Many studies proved that the C-section has inverse association with the early initiation of breastfeeding. According to a study conducted in Turkey, the systematized

incidence rate of late breastfeeding initiation was 35.3% among mothers who had a vaginal delivery, versus 50.5% among those who had a C-section delivery (Erbaydar and Erbaydar, 2020). In addition, the results another study showed that The rate of initiation of breastfeeding in the first hour after delivery was considerably higher in the vaginal delivery group (82%) than in the C-section delivery group (38%), and the rate of formula feeding was higher in the C-section group (33%) than in the vaginal delivery group (22%) (Islami *et al.*, 2009).

Pre-lacteal feeding is a well-known barrier to proper breastfeeding proved by this study. Literature supported this evidence that prelacteal feeding deprives infants of colostrum rich in many nutrients and immunoglobulins, thus resulting in reducing gastrointestinal priming and increasing the rate of infant mortality and morbidity (Agho *et al.*, 2016). According to a survey conducted in India, the percentages of prelacteal feeding and timely breastfeeding initiation were 16.9% and 36.4% respectively. Along with other factors prelacteal feeding and delayed breastfeeding initiation were found to have a substantial association (Patel *et al.*, 2013). A meta-analysis in Ethiopia and a study in South Sudan revealed that, the prevalence of pre-lacteal feeding was 25.28% and 53% respectively (Temesgen *et al.*, 2018; Tongun *et al.*, 2018), while the prevalence in recent study was recorded 42%.

Maternal employment status was not associated with breastfeeding initiation and exclusive breastfeeding in the present study sample. However, the previous research finding suggested that Maternal employment has an impact on childcare time and is cited as a primary cause for low exclusive breastfeeding rates and breastfeeding duration (Chekol *et al.*, 2017). A study was performed in Korea concluded that the rates of breastfeeding initiation were same in employed and unemployed mothers. At all duration points, continuation rates declined for both types of mothers, but were considerably lower among employed mothers (Kang *et al.*, 2015).

Hospital staff knowledge, attitudes, and behavior towards breastfeeding had a great impact on the initiation of breastfeeding in this present study. Several studies have found a strong link between the implementation of Baby-Friendly practices and

breastfeeding. A study conducted to assess the knowledge of nurses regarding breastfeeding resulted that the nurses limited education, hospital lactation policies, high rates of surgical delivery, and non-serious attitudes of nurses were all barriers to best practices in breastfeeding initiation (Weddig *et al.*, 2011).

In this study, there was no association found between the discard of colostrum and the initiation of breastfeeding. Although the percentage of mothers discarding colostrum was high in the current study (45.3%) due to lack of knowledge regarding the importance of colostrum for the newborn. WHO and UNICEF suggested colostrum feeding during the initial days after birth due to its several health benefits for the infant? In this regard, a cross-sectional study was conducted in Northeastern Ethiopia to check the importance of colostrum intake in improving the nutritional status of preschool children. The results of the chi-square test indicated that colostrum feeding had an association with three indicators of the malnourished child i.e., underweight, stunting, and wasting. It was concluded that feeding of colostrum has an association with lower chances of malnutrition in preschool children (Liben *et al.*, 2016).

According to literature, colostrum feeding prevents many viral, bacterial, fungal, and protozoal infections in neonates (Yeshambel Wassic *et al.*, 2020). The percentage of mothers knowing the importance of colostrum was comparatively lower than a study in Saudi Arabia (89.3%) and the trends observed in Ethiopia, i.e., 60.2% (Al-Binali, 2012; Tadele *et al.*, 2016). The differences in results can be due to sociodemographic variations. Another study showed almost similar results (Joshin *et al.*, 2012). Other findings of a study suggested that only 6% of females were aware of the nutritious values of colostrum for the newborn. About 35% of females believed that there is something toxic that is not healthy for the baby, and 15% believed that colostrum should discard before breastfeeding (Aisha *et al.*, 2016). hour rooming-in has been found a positive association with early initiation of breastfeeding, according to the current study. Approximately 51% of mothers had 24-hour rooming-in with their babies, and 49% of mothers were far away from them. The results were compared with the previous studies which

elaborated that the success of exclusive breastfeeding is not certainly dependent upon 24-hour rooming-in (Mcrae 2019). In another study, it was seen that the infant with an average breastfeeding rate at the age of 3 to 4 months had higher 24-hour rooming-in proportion (Ng *et al.*, 2019).

Conclusion

The current study sought to determine the possible association between breastfeeding initiation and exclusive breastfeeding with sociodemographic factors, pregnancy-related issues, experience in the hospital during the stay after delivery, and ultimately the factors that can hinder exclusive breastfeeding in the different hospitals of Faisalabad, and mothers were asked regarding their knowledge about breastfeeding importance and then counsel them to improve exclusive breastfeeding.

The result findings confirmed the importance of medical conditions during pregnancy, knowledge given during antenatal visits, C-sections, pre-lacteal feeding, staff assistance in breastfeeding, 24-hour rooming-in, recommendation of formula milk by doctors, Staff advice regarding positioning before discharge, and staff suggestions about how to resolve breastfeeding issues for the initiation of breastfeeding and exclusive breastfeeding up to 6 months. Other factors like sociodemographic information, number of miscarriages, number of antenatal visits, gestational age, and discard of colostrum found no association between with any type of breastfeeding.

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